

Soluble endoglin as a biomarker of cardiovascular and metabolic disorders related to endothelial dysfunction: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Sixteen included studies were published between 1996 and 2025
- sENG serum/plasma concentrations are higher in cardiovascular and metabolic disorders related to endothelial dysfunction
- sENG serum/plasma concentrations were elevated in patients with DM1, DM2, and heart failure.
- sENG might represent a novel biomarker reflecting endothelial damage only in patients with DM1, DM2, and heart failure.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT

Background and aims: Soluble endoglin (sENG) has been discussed as a biomarker of endothelial dysfunction, associated with cardiovascular and metabolic disorders. A critical evaluation of sENG as a diagnostic tool for atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases (ASCVD), type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM1), type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2), hypertensive disorders, and heart failure (HF) using a meta-analysis has never been performed.

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Methods: PUBMED, SCOPUS, and Web of Science databases were searched up to August 1, 2025. Information on sENG concentrations in the group with one of the above-mentioned diagnoses and the control group was extracted and analyzed. Publication bias and quality assessment were performed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) criteria.

Results: 16 studies were evaluated. A total of 2113 subjects were included, comprising 1391 subjects in disease groups and 722 in the control group. sENG serum/plasma concentrations were significantly higher in disorders related to endothelial dysfunction than in controls, with a pooled mean difference of 0.92 ng/mL (95% CI: 0.50–1.34, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, sENG serum/plasma concentrations were significantly elevated in patients with DM1, 0.99 ng/mL (95% CI 0.45–1.54, $p < 0.001$), DM2, 1.98 ng/mL (95% CI 0.60–3.35, $p = 0.005$) and HF, 1.06 ng/mL (95% CI 0.06–2.06, $p = 0.038$), compared to controls.

Conclusions: This meta-analysis is the first to demonstrate that sENG serum/plasma concentrations are significantly higher in selected cardiovascular and metabolic disorders related to endothelial dysfunction. sENG might represent a novel biomarker reflecting endothelial damage only in patients with DM1, DM2, and heart failure.

1. Introduction

Endoglin (CD105, ENG) is a homodimeric transmembrane glycoprotein primarily expressed on proliferating endothelial cells and serves as a co-receptor for transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) signaling. It plays a critical role in vascular development, angiogenesis, and endothelial cell proliferation [1]. Soluble endoglin (sENG) can be characterized as the extracellular domain of membrane-bound endoglin, which enters the systemic circulation under various conditions associated with endothelial injury, activation, inflammation, or senescence [2]. In addition to the currently known metalloproteinases responsible for cleaving endoglin into the circulation, specifically MMP-14 [3] and MMP-12 [4], it was recently reported that thrombin can also cleave endoglin from the endothelium [5].

Today, the endothelium is recognized as a dynamic organ with secretory, synthetic, metabolic, and immunological functions. Endothelial cells play an indispensable role in regulating vascular tone and permeability, angiogenesis, and mediating hemostatic, inflammatory, and reparative responses to local injury. To perform these functions, the endothelium is highly active and constantly responds to mechanical, biochemical, and toxic stimuli [6–8]. Disruption of endothelial homeostasis by damaging factors leads to the development of endothelial dysfunction, which is a key pathophysiological feature of various cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, including hypertension, hyperglycemia/diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, and atherosclerosis [9].

Since cardiovascular diseases and the burden attributable to metabolic risks are leading causes of death worldwide [10,11], the search for early diagnostic tools is of great importance. One possible strategy is to identify reliable markers of endothelial dysfunction, although this represents a demanding and highly complex approach [12]. Soluble endoglin has been discussed for several years as a promising molecule of this type and has been proposed as a novel biomarker of endothelial dysfunction [13], closely associated with the aforementioned cardiovascular and metabolic disorders [14,15]. However, the reliability of using sENG as a biomarker for specific pathological conditions has not yet been evaluated through a meta-analysis. This study was therefore the first of its kind and assessed the role of sENG in cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, in which its serum/plasma concentrations are most commonly measured in human medicine. Specifically, it focused on a group of diseases related to endothelial dysfunction and associated with atherosclerosis, known as ASCVD (atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases), type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM1), type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2), arterial hypertension (hypertensive disorders), and heart failure (HF).

2. Methods

2.1. Search strategy

This study was designed according to the guidelines for Meta-analysis and Systematic Reviews of Observational Studies (MOOSE) statement [16]. PubMed-Medline, SCOPUS and Web of Science databases were searched using the following search terms in titles and

abstracts (also in combination with MESH terms): ((serum endoglin) OR (soluble endoglin) OR (CD105) OR (plasma endoglin) AND ((diabetes mellitus type I) OR (diabetes mellitus type II) OR (heart failure) OR (arterial hypertension) OR (myocardial infarction) OR (coronary syndrome) OR (ischemic heart disease) OR (atherosclerosis)) AND (control) NOT (cancer) NOT (autoimmunity) NOT (therapy) NOT (preeclampsia) NOT (*in vitro*) NOT (*in vivo*) NOT (mice)). The wild-card term “*” was used to increase the sensitivity of the search strategy. We complemented the searches by perusing the references of retrieved articles on the relevant topic. The search was limited to articles published in the English language. The literature was searched from inception to August 01, 2025.

2.2. Study selection

Original studies were included if they met the following inclusion criteria: (i) full-text article available online, (ii) relevant cardiovascular and/or metabolic disease diagnosis, (iii) presence of a healthy control group, (iv) presentation of sufficient information on sENG concentrations in the group with diagnosis and the control group. Exclusion criteria were (i) interventional trials, (ii) lack of a healthy control group, (iii) lack of sufficient information on sENG concentrations in the group with diagnosis and the control group, (iv) cancer, preeclampsia or autoimmunity nature of disease, (v) *in vitro* or *in vivo* nature of the study.

2.3. Data extraction

Eligible studies were reviewed, and the following data were abstracted: 1) first author's name; 2) year of publication; 3) study location; 4) study design; 5) number of participants in the diagnosis and control groups; 6) data regarding concentrations of sENG in the diagnosis and control groups (including sample nature and method of assessment).

2.4. Quality assessment

Quality assessment was performed using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) criteria for observational studies. Since we utilized the baseline characteristics of all three prospective cohort studies included [17–19], we did not specify the outcome category in NOS. The case-control version of NOS was used for all included studies. This tool evaluates studies in three main categories: Selection, Comparability, and Exposure. Studies rated with ≤ 3 , 4–7, and ≥ 8 stars are categorized as low, medium, and high quality, respectively [20,21].

2.5. Data synthesis and statistical analysis

Comprehensive Meta-Analysis software (version 2) was used in the current study [22]. When studies reported median (IQR) values, they were converted to mean (SD) values. Additionally, if a study reported soluble endoglin values for different subtypes of a single disease (e.g. diabetic patients with and without nephropathy), the results of these subtypes were pooled and entered as a case group. Subgroup analysis by

disease type was also conducted. Publication bias was evaluated using a funnel plot and Egger's linear regression test. Trim and fill analysis was conducted in the case of probable evidence of publication bias. Sensitivity analysis was also conducted to assess the robustness of the results.

3. Results

3.1. Study selection

Electronic searches and complementary hand-searching retrieved one hundred and thirty-eight articles. From this number of publications, fifty-nine were removed for duplication. From the remaining seventy-nine articles, sixty-one were excluded based on their title and abstract for not meeting the inclusion criteria. After careful assessment of the final eighteen full-text articles eligible, two studies were excluded (one for the reason of intervention and one presented a duplicate report). At the end of the selection process, sixteen articles [17–19,23–35] met the inclusion criteria and were selected for meta-analysis. A summary of the study selection process is shown in Fig. 1.

3.2. Characteristics of included studies

Included studies were published between 1996 and 2025; all of them

were observational studies. A total of 2113 subjects were included in the sixteen eligible studies, comprising 1391 subjects in disease groups and 722 in the control group. The largest study had a population size of 255 subjects [17], while the smallest study recruited 36 subjects [30]. All the selected studies were performed in subjects with relevant cardiovascular and/or metabolic disease related to endothelial dysfunction; sENG levels in either plasma or serum samples were assessed by ELISA in all studies. Diseases were grouped as follows: DM1 group, DM2 group, hypertensive disorders group (hypertension, pulmonary arterial hypertension), heart failure group (left ventricular dysfunction, heart failure), and ASCVD group (stroke, atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction).

DM1 disease group included two studies conducted in Turkey [23, 29], and studies conducted in Egypt [31], and the United Kingdom [33]. DM2 disease group included studies conducted in Spain [25], Egypt [26], China [27], Turkey [28], and Egypt [34]. The ASCVD group included studies conducted in the United Kingdom [24], Spain [17], China [18], and the Czech Republic [35]. The heart failure disease group included two studies, both conducted in the USA [19,30]. The hypertensive disorders group included studies conducted in Spain [25] and the USA [32]. In one study [22] assessing sENG plasma concentrations in two pathologies (DM2 and hypertension) [25], two separate disease groups were reported (DM2 in study A and hypertension in study B). For meta-analysis, the number of control individuals was halved for each of

Fig. 1.

them (33 for study A and 32 for study B). One study [30] was reported as two separate studies in a heart failure disease group (smokers with heart failure and non-smokers with heart failure, both with relevant controls). Five studies [25,26,28,29,34] did not report overall patient data and only reported subgroup data. For meta-analysis, the mean and standard deviation data were pooled, and a single data point was reported for the patient group. Demographic characteristics of the included studies are shown in Table 1.

3.3. sENG as a biomarker of cardiovascular and metabolic disorders

This meta-analysis shows that sENG serum/plasma concentrations are significantly higher in selected cardiovascular and metabolic disorders related to endothelial dysfunction (compared to controls), with a pooled mean difference of 0.92 ng/mL (95% CI: 0.50–1.34, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 2). Moreover, the pooled effect size remained consistent even after removing each study, demonstrating the robustness of the result (Fig. 3).

In addition, we analyzed sENG concentrations in DM1 and DM2, HF, ASCVD, and hypertensive disorders. The results revealed sENG serum/plasma concentrations are significantly elevated in patients with DM1, 0.99 ng/mL (95% CI 0.45–1.54, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 4). Similarly, sENG serum/plasma concentrations are significantly elevated in patients with DM2, 1.98 ng/mL (95% CI 0.60–3.35, $p = 0.005$) (Fig. 4). Interestingly, significantly higher sENG serum/plasma concentrations were also detected in HF patients compared to controls, 1.06 ng/mL (95% CI 0.06–2.06, $p = 0.038$) (Fig. 4). On the other hand, sENG serum/plasma concentrations were not significantly elevated in ASCVD patients, 0.03 ng/mL (95% CI –0.43 to 0.49, $p = 0.896$), and hypertensive disorders patients, 0.33 ng/mL (95% CI –1.93 to 2.60, $p = 0.773$) (Fig. 4).

3.4. Quality assessment

A systematic assessment of bias in the included studies was performed using the NOS criteria. As shown in Table 2, none of the included studies were classified as low quality according to NOS.

3.5. Publication bias

Finally, the potential for publication bias must be acknowledged (Fig. 5). The asymmetry of the funnel plot raises concerns that smaller, negative studies may be underreported, leading to an overestimation of the true effect (P -value for the Egger test < 0.05). The trim and fill method was used to adjust the asymmetry. As shown in Fig. 5, the imputed estimate (0.89) matches the previously observed estimate (0.92), indicating that the results are robust.

4. Discussion

In this meta-analysis, we show for the first time that sENG serum/plasma concentrations are significantly higher in patients with selected cardiovascular and metabolic disorders related to endothelial dysfunction, especially in patients with DM1, DM2, and heart failure.

sENG is a cleavage product of membrane ENG, which is expressed by various cell types, including endothelial cells [36], liver sinusoidal endothelial cells (LSECs) [37], fibroblasts [38], hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) [39], activated monocytes, and macrophages [40]. It was reported that sENG is increased in various pathological conditions that reflect the development of endothelial dysfunction both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [37,41,42].

Thus, in this meta-analysis, we hypothesized that sENG serum/plasma concentration would be elevated in cardiovascular and metabolic disorders related to endothelial dysfunction, including ASCVD, DM1, DM2, hypertensive disorders, and HF.

Meta-analysis results revealed that sENG serum/plasma concentrations are significantly higher in these selected disorders. However, once we focused on particular disorders, it was shown that a significant

relation is valid mainly for DM1, DM2, and HF patients.

The most prominent increase in sENG was observed in the study by Ibrahim et al., where they focused on children and adolescents with DM1 [31]. Interestingly, other studies have also shown elevated sENG concentrations in DM1 children and adolescents [23,31,33], suggesting that sENG might be a sensitive biomarker in patients with DM1.

More heterogeneous results were observed in patients with DM2. In general, the chosen studies showed that sENG serum/plasma concentrations are higher in patients with DM2 compared to healthy controls. DM2 is characterized by the development and progression of later clinical complications, such as diabetic neuropathy, retinopathy, or nephropathy [43]. Interestingly, sENG serum/plasma concentrations in relation to these severe clinical complications are inconclusive; however, Motawi et al. proposed that sENG plasma concentration reflects the presence of neuropathy in patients with DM2 [34].

Additionally, Blazquez-Medela et al. showed a correlation of sENG with endothelial dysfunction in patients with arterial hypertension and DM2, as well as its association with retinopathy and left ventricular hypertrophy in these groups [25]. On the other hand, other studies showed that sENG did not reflect the presence of normoalbuminuria or microalbuminuria in patients with DM2 and diabetic nephropathy, despite sENG serum concentrations being higher in both groups compared to the control [27,28]. Thus, we might propose that during the early stages of DM2, sENG serum concentrations may initially rise. However, as other complications develop, these concentrations may subsequently decline or stay steady. This pattern suggests that elevated sENG serum concentrations could be associated with early diabetes-induced functional vascular changes, potentially appearing even before the onset of microalbuminuria or other subclinical structural vascular abnormalities in DM2.

Except for diabetic patients, we focused on cardiovascular pathological situations where endothelial dysfunction is expected to be part of the pathophysiology and clinical consequences. Meta-analysis results showed that sENG serum/plasma concentrations were increased in all included heart failure studies, suggesting a strong association and supporting its potential use as both a diagnostic and a prognostic biomarker. Kapur et al. showed that elevated sENG serum concentrations can serve as a sensitive biomarker of increased cardiac filling pressure [19]. In cardiac tissue, ENG is expressed by endothelial cells, fibroblasts within the connective tissue surrounding muscle fibers, and fibroblast-like stromal cells of the valve leaflets, whereas cardiac myocytes show little to no detectable ENG expression [38]. Since progressive heart failure is characterized by cardiac fibrosis, fibrosis development was shown to be possibly related to increased cleavage and release of sENG. Interestingly, sENG has also been reported as a biomarker of liver fibrosis [44]. Thus, we might speculate that pathological fibrosis development in any organ, including the heart, might be related to increased cleavage of ENG and increased serum/plasma concentration of sENG. Moreover, it is important to recognize that these patients have also developed endothelial dysfunction in other parts of the vasculature (not just in the heart), and sENG can be cleaved from the affected endothelial cells as well.

In this meta-analysis, we also demonstrated that sENG serum/plasma concentrations were highly variable in hypertensive patients. sENG serum concentrations were elevated in pulmonary arterial hypertension patients [32], which would support the interpretation that circulating sENG reflects endothelial activation, proliferation, and active pulmonary vascular remodeling [45]. On the other hand, Blazquez-Medela et al. study showed that sENG concentrations were lower in arterial hypertension patients compared to controls [25].

Lastly, sENG serum/plasma concentration in ASCVD patients showed controversial outcomes. There were two studies that showed significantly increased serum/plasma concentrations of sENG with respect to ASCVD [24,35]. Rathouska et al. analyzed patients admitted for the first manifestation of myocardial infarction (MI) and with no history of cardiovascular protective treatment use before the event. They concluded that

Table 1

Demographic characteristics of included studies. Values are expressed as mean ± (SD), (SE), or median (interquartile range). Abbreviations: NS, not stated; BMI, body mass index; DM1, diabetes mellitus type 1; DM2, diabetes mellitus type 2. aDM2 without hypertension; DM2 with hypertension, bDM2 with normalalbuminuria; DM2 with microalbuminuria, cDM2 with normalalbuminuria; DM2 with nephropathy, dDM1 with normalalbuminuria; DM1 with microalbuminuria, esmokers with heart failure; non-smokers with heart failure, fsmoker controls; non-smoker controls, gDM2 without peripheral neuropathy; DM2 with peripheral neuropathy.

Study	Location	Design	Disease	Participants		Age (years)		Gender		BMI (kg/m ²)		Smoking		sENG levels (ng/mL)		Samples	Method
				Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group		
Anik et al. (2020)	Turkey	Case-control study	DM1	64	64	12.5 ± 3.6	11.6 ± 3.9	♂ (29), ♀ (35)	♂ (32), ♀ (32)	NS	NS	NS	NS	7.37 ± 1.28	5.89 ± 1.70	serum	ELISA (Sigma-Aldrich)
Blann et al. (1996)	UK	Case-control study	atherosclerosis	57	26	60 ± 8	56 ± 7	♂ (46), ♀ (11)	♂ (18), ♀ (8)	NS	NS	11 (19%)	3 (12%)	5.9 (0.1-77.8)	3.0 (0.1-21)	serum	ELISA (in-house)
Blázquez-Medela et al. (2010) A	Spain	Case-control study	hypertension	159	65	56.69 ± 11.08	48.75 ± 11.22	♂ (100), ♀ (59)	♂ (35), ♀ (30)	28.68 ± 3.93	26.82 ± 3.29	43 (26.81%)	16 (24.61%)	4.39 ± 1.04	5.21 ± 1.10	plasma	ELISA (R&D systems)
Blázquez-Medela et al. (2010) B	Spain	Case-control study	DM2	64	65	53.27 ± 12.74; 62.17 ± 8.03 ^a	48.75 ± 11.22	♂ (18), ♀ (4); ♂ (28), ♀ (14) ^a	♂ (35), ♀ (30)	28.71 ± 4.99; 30.33 ± 4.86 ^a	26.82 ± 3.29	8 (36.36%); 7 (16.67%) ^a	16 (24.61%)	5.02 ± 0.98; 4.88 ± 1.20 ^a	5.21 ± 1.10	plasma	ELISA (R&D systems)
Cruz-Gonzalez et al. (2008)	Spain	Case-control study	myocardial infarction	183	72	70.6 ± 11.6	69 ± 10	♂ (124), ♀ (59)	♂ (47), ♀ (25)	NS	NS	NS	NS	4.25 ± 0.99	4.59 ± 0.87	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)
Doghish et al. (2019)	Egypt	Case-control study	DM2	68	13	56.63 ± 5.47; 57.16 ± 5.93 ^b	52.92 ± 6.97	♂ (28), ♀ (40)	♂ (7), ♀ (6)	33.91 ± 3.39; 33.52 ± 4.19 ^b	27.33 ± 4.75	NS	NS	9.595 ± 3.49; 8.827 ± 2.67 ^b	1.747 ± 0.93	plasma	ELISA (R&D systems)
Dou et al. (2023)	China	Case-control study	DM2	34	53	49.70 ± 9.25	47.44 ± 10.54	♂ (25), ♀ (9)	♂ (28), ♀ (25)	26.7 ± 3.77	23.95 ± 2.64	NS	NS	7.63 ± 2.67 pg/mL	5.40 ± 2.27 pg/mL	serum	ELISA (Westang Biotech)
Ekiz-Bilir et al. (2016)	Turkey	Case-control study	DM2	96	35	56.36 ± 8.55; 55.17 ± 6.68 ^c	57.31 ± 8.41	♂ (52), ♀ (44)	♂ (18), ♀ (17)	NS	NS	NS	NS	20.96 (12.0-34.86); 24.05 (10.0-53.0) ^c	20.58 (11.06-58.85)	serum	ELISA (PRC)
Emeksiz et al. (2016)	Turkey	Case-control study	DM1	58	29	15.14 ± 1.55; 16.3 ± 2.17 ^d	15.03 ± 1.97	♂ (22), ♀ (36)	♂ (14), ♀ (15)	NS	NS	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2.5 (2.19-3.09); 2.21 (1.91-2.90) ^d	1.97 (1.72-2.23)	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)
He et al. (2018)	China	Case-control study	stroke	114	114	72.5 ± 9.0	72.1 ± 9.3	♂ (74), ♀ (40)	♂ (74), ♀ (40)	23.0 ± 3.3	23.6 ± 3.5	54 (47.4%)	37 (32.5%)	2.49 ± 1.13	2.53 ± 1.11	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)
Heffernan et al. (2011)	USA	Case-control study	heart failure	18	18	57 ± 4; 59 ± 5 ^e	62 ± 3; 59 ± 3 ^f	♂ (6), ♀ (12)	♂ (7), ♀ (11)	NS	NS	8 (44%)	7 (39%)	4.111 ± 0.217; 5.305 ± 0.274 ^e	3.554 ± 0.209; 3.372 ± 0.152 ^f	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)
Ibrahim et al. (2020)	Egypt	Case-control study	DM1	120	100	13.5 ± 3.2	12.1 ± 2.8	♂ (54), ♀ (66)	♂ (41), ♀ (59)	18.9 ± 2.3	18.1 ± 3.1	NS	NS	31 (19-75)	28.5 (16.8-43)	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Study	Location	Design	Disease	Participants		Age (years)		Gender		BMI (kg/m ²)		Smoking		sENG levels (ng/mL)		Samples	Method
				Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group	Disease group	Control group		
Kapur et al. (2010)	USA	Case-control study	heart failure	82	25	21-80	21-80	♂ (53), ♀ (29)	NS	NS	NS	13 (16%)	NS	4.257 ± 0.966	3.589 ± 0.588	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)
Malhotra et al. (2013)	USA	Case-control study	pulmonary arterial hypertension	97	56	48.9 ± 13.1	47.4 ± 8.0	♂ (10), ♀ (87)	♂ (8), ♀ (48)	NS	NS	NS	NS	5.15 ± 0.15	3.66 ± 0.12	serum	ELISA (R&D systems)
Malik et al. (2005)	UK	Case-control study	DM1	38	15	NS	30 (21.5-33.5)	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	1.8 (1.1-2.8)	0.7 (0.3-1.8)	plasma	ELISA (in-house)
Motawi et al. (2014)	Egypt	Case-control study	DM2	60	20	55.15 ± 8.9	51.85 ± 9.8	♂ (41), ♀ (19)	♂ (12), ♀ (8)	26.2 ± 4.2; 28.3 ± 4.4 ^g	25.78 ± 4.17	NS	NS	1.87 ± 0.336; 2.3 ± 0.12g	1.13 ± 0.4	plasma	ELISA (EIAB)
Rathouska et al. (2025)	Czech Republic	Case-control study	myocardial infarction	79	17	54.1 ± 8.9	51.5 ± 8.6	♂ (65), ♀ (14)	♂ (9), ♀ (8)	26.6 ± 3.6	28.2 ± 4.4	51 (65%)	3 (18%)	4.56 (3.97-5.12)	3.92 (3.62-4.69)	plasma	ELISA (R&D systems)

Values are expressed as mean ± (SD), (SE) or median (interquartile range).

Abbreviations: NS, not stated; BMI, body mass index; DM1, diabetes mellitus type 1; DM2, diabetes mellitus type 2.

^a DM2 without hypertension; DM2 with hypertension.

^b DM2 with normalalbuminuria; DM2 with microalbuminuria.

^c DM2 with normalalbuminuria; DM2 with nephropathy.

^d DM1 with normalalbuminuria; DM1 with microalbuminuria.

^e Smokers with heart failure; non-smokers with heart failure.

^f Smoker controls; non-smoker controls.

^g DM2 without peripheral neuropathy; DM2 with peripheral neuropathy.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Group by Disease Subgroup	Study name	Statistics for each study				
		Difference in means	Standard error	Lower limit	Upper limit	p-Value
ASCVD	Blann, 1996	6.390	3.496	-0.462	13.242	0.068
ASCVD	Cruz-Gonzalez, 2008	-0.340	0.133	-0.601	-0.079	0.011
ASCVD	He, 2018	-0.040	0.148	-0.331	0.251	0.787
ASCVD	Rathouska, 2025	0.480	0.235	0.019	0.941	0.041
ASCVD		0.031	0.234	-0.428	0.490	0.896
DM1	Emeksiz, 2016	0.500	0.144	0.218	0.782	0.001
DM1	Anik, 2020	1.480	0.266	0.959	2.001	0.000
DM1	Ibrahim, 2020	12.770	4.572	3.809	21.731	0.005
DM1	Malik, 2005	0.970	0.104	0.766	1.174	0.000
DM1		0.994	0.276	0.452	1.535	0.000
DM2	Blázquez-Medela, 2010 (A)	-0.260	0.240	-0.730	0.210	0.279
DM2	Doghish, 2019	7.460	0.904	5.688	9.232	0.000
DM2	Ekiz-Bilir, 2016	-0.350	1.774	-3.826	3.126	0.844
DM2	Dou, 2023	2.230	0.535	1.182	3.278	0.000
DM2	Motawi, 2013	0.955	0.069	0.819	1.091	0.000
DM2		1.975	0.700	0.603	3.347	0.005
HF	Heffeman, 2011 (A)	0.560	0.112	0.341	0.779	0.000
HF	Heffeman, 2011 (B)	1.930	0.094	1.746	2.114	0.000
HF	Kapur, 2010	0.670	0.202	0.273	1.067	0.001
HF		1.059	0.510	0.059	2.060	0.038
hypertensive disorders	Blázquez-Medela, 2010 (B)	-0.820	0.203	-1.219	-0.421	0.000
hypertensive disorders	Malhotra, 2013	1.490	0.218	1.063	1.917	0.000
hypertensive disorders		0.334	1.155	-1.930	2.597	0.773

Fig. 4.

Table 2

Quality assessment of the included studies on soluble endoglin and diseases related to endothelial dysfunction according to the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) criteria.

Study	Selection (Max 4 stars)	Comparability (Max 2 stars)	Exposure (Max 3 stars)	Total Star
Anik, 2020	3	2	3	8
Blann, 1996	3	1	3	7
Blázquez-Medela, 2010	3	0	3	6
Cruz-Gonzalez, 2008 ^a	4	1	3	8
Doghish, 2019	3	0	3	6
Dou, 2023	3	0	3	6
Ekiz-Bilir, 2016	4	2	3	9
Emeksiz, 2016	3	1	3	7
He, 2018 ^a	4	1	3	8
Heffeman, 2011	3	0	3	6
Ibrahim, 2020	4	2	3	9
Kapur, 2010 ^a	4	0	3	7
Malhotra, 2013	3	1	3	7
Malik, 2005	1	1	3	5
Motawi, 2013	4	1	3	8
Rathouska, 2025	4	1	3	8

^a These studies were prospective cohort studies, but the extracted data were reported at baseline.

sENG could serve as a biomarker reflecting endothelial dysfunction in myocardial infarction patients without prior treatment for cardiovascular risk factors [35]. Blann et al. analyzed survivors of ischemic heart disease 6 weeks after the event and patients with confirmed peripheral vascular disease and confirmed atherosclerosis. These data are in line with previous reports from experimental studies, where endothelial dysfunction [42] and atherosclerosis [46] resulted in elevation of sENG concentrations.

On the contrary, He et al. and Cruz-Gonzalez et al. showed opposite results. Cruz-Gonzalez study demonstrated that sENG serum concentrations were significantly lower in myocardial infarction patients upon admission to the hospital and 48 h later, and sENG serum concentrations were also lower in patients who died compared to patients who survived, suggesting that sENG was an independent predictor of short-term cardiovascular mortality in MI patients [17]. Similarly, He et al. evaluated the association between sENG serum concentrations and large-artery atherosclerotic stroke. sENG serum concentrations were not significantly different between patients and controls [18].

Possible explanation of these inconclusive results can come from the fact that sENG might be released from various parts of the vasculature with different stages of endothelial dysfunction and atherosclerosis, and these studies did not evaluate precisely the type of lesions and their localization.

5. Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations. The included cohorts exhibited considerable heterogeneity, largely attributable to our focus on disease-specific endothelial dysfunction. We excluded studies in which the conditions were pharmacologically treated and included only studies with an appropriate control group. As a result, sex-related differences could not be assessed in this meta-analysis.

In addition, the inclusion criteria used in this meta-analysis limited the number of studies that assessed sENG in patients with ASCVD and hypertension. Consequently, based on the currently available evidence, sENG cannot be considered a reliable biomarker for ASCVD, as well as for hypertensive disorders.

Another potential limitation is our inability to determine the organ and vascular origin of cleaved sENG. Notably, the cleavage of sENG from membrane-bound endoglin has been described in various types of blood vessels across different segments of the vascular bed during the development of endothelial dysfunction [42], atherosclerosis [46], and liver diseases (liver sinusoidal endothelial dysfunction) [37], so it is supposed to be related to the dysfunction of endothelial cells or vascular damage. Based on this, we propose that sENG is rather a biomarker of endothelial

Fig. 5.

dysfunction than a metabolic biomarker of cardiometabolic disorders evaluated in this study.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, this meta-analysis of 16 selected studies demonstrates, for the first time, that sENG serum/plasma concentrations are elevated and may reflect endothelial damage, particularly in patients with DM1, DM2, and heart failure – conditions representing cardiovascular and metabolic disorders associated with endothelial dysfunction. These findings suggest that sENG might serve as a promising novel biomarker in such disorders.

Data availability statement

The original contributions of this study are detailed in the article; further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, Jana Urbankova Rathouska and Petr Nachtigal; Methodology, Jana Urbankova Rathouska, Maryam Emadzadeh, Tannaz Jamialahmadi, Amirhossein Sahebkar; Validation, Jana Urbankova Rathouska, Maryam Emadzadeh, Tannaz Jamialahmadi, Amirhossein Sahebkar; Formal Analysis, Jana Urbankova Rathouska and Petr Nachtigal; Data Curation, Jana Urbankova Rathouska, Maryam Emadzadeh, Tannaz Jamialahmadi, Amirhossein Sahebkar, Petr Nachtigal; Writing—original draft preparation, Jana Urbankova Rathouska and Petr Nachtigal; Writing—review and editing, Jana Urbankova Rathouska, Maryam Emadzadeh, Ivana Nemeckova, Petra Fikrova, Katarina Tripiska, Tannaz Jamialahmadi, Amirhossein Sahebkar, Petr Nachtigal; Project Administration, Petr Nachtigal; Funding Acquisition, Petr Nachtigal. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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